

Информационен резонанс на книгата „Interior Chinatown” на Charles Yu

Информационен мониторинг и библиометричен анализ
(2020-2023)

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Дата: 09.06.2023 г.

Увод

Обект на настоящото проучване е книгата „Interior Chinatown” („Вътрешен Чайнатаун“) на Чарлс Ю. Мотивите за избор на обекта са високите очаквания на нейните издатели и противоречивите коментари, отзиви и критики за нея, след като беше публикувана и разпространена в книготърговските мрежи.

Целта на настоящото проучване е да открие, представи и обобщи всички форми на информационен резонанс на книгата „Interior Chinatown” и на база тази обратна връзка да се провери хипотезата, че книгата се е осъществила като медия.

Задачите на проучването включват намиране и представяне на различните форми на обратна връзка с автора относно книгата във всяка от осемте фази на алгоритъма за информационно търсене на информационен резонанс на книга,

обобщаване и визуализиране на данните чрез диаграми, рекапитулация на резултатите чрез количествено обобщение и да се направи извод, като се отговори на въпроса дали книгата се е осъществила като медия.

Методиката на работа, която ще бъде използвана в настоящето проучване, включва информационно търсене, информационен мониторинг и библиометричен анализ. За извършването на библиометричния анализ ще бъде използван инструментът „Алгоритъм за информационно търсене на информационния резонанс на книга в 8 фази”, разработен от М. Цветкова.¹

Обхватът на проучването включва пълното издание на книгата. Информационният мониторинг включва всички български и чуждестранни канали, които могат да дадат информационен резонанс на книгата. Няма ограничения в езика. Изследването обхваща периода от 2020 г. до 2023 г.

Обект на изследването (английски оригинал):

Author:	Charles Yu
Title:	Interior Chinatown
Publisher:	New York, Pantheon Books 2020
Edition/Format:	Print book: Fiction
Subjects:	Generic Asian Man -- Fiction. Race -- Fiction. Immigration -- Fiction.
Genre/Form:	Fiction
Document Type:	Book
All Authors / Contributors:	Charles Yu
ISBN:	978-0307907196
OCLC Number:	1343739319
Description	270 pages ; 20 cm

¹ Tsvetkova, Milena. Reading as Communication Echo: Scientific Model of the Reader's Feedback Research. Saarbrücken, Germany: Lambert Academic Publishing, 2017. 120 p. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3204060>

Изобр.1. Корица на книгата на „Interior Chinatown” (2020)

Информационно-резонансното (медийно-рефлексивното) поле на книгата „Вътрешен Чайнатаун - реакциите на читателите ѝ във вид на обратна връзка, ще бъде проследено чрез информационен мониторинг по 8 основни фази:

- I. Симултанни онлайн практики и директна обратна връзка с автора;
- II. Номинална (формална) обработка - библиографско описание, преиздание;
- III. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието - класифициране, предметизиране (извеждане на ключови думи); анонси, анотации, резюме, реферат; съкратени версии на книгата;
- IV. Репродукция (деривация) - цитиране, перифразиране, ремиксиране, фен творчество (фенфикшън), преводи;
- V. Текуща (оперативна) критика - ревю (преглед); търговски и читателски класации;
- VI. Експертна (научна) критика - професионални награди; изследвания и интерпретации;

VII. Медиаморфози (медийни репрезентации, продължения, трансакции, транскодиране, трансмутации, конвертиране на книгата в друг медийен формат) - екранизиране на книгата, поставяне на сцена като театрална постановка и други практики, форми и изкуства, появили се в следствие на прочита на книгата;

VIII. Историзация (меморизация и митологизация).

Фаза 1. Симултани онлайн практики и директна обратна връзка с автора

В тази фаза ще бъдат отразени коментари в социалните мрежи Goodreads и Library Thing. Ще бъдат търсени и представени само коментари с текст без ограничение в езика, както и примери за директна обратна връзка с автора. Ще бъдат търсени и коментари в български онлайн книжарници (ozone.bg; helikon.bg; hermesbooks.bg; ciela.com; knizhen-pazar.net).

Коментари в Goodreads:

Interior Chinatown. In: Goodreads, 2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/44436221-interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Най-стари:

“Now Winner of the National Book Award for Fiction 2020

You have to applaud Yu for crafting a unique narrative set-up: His novel merges the storyline of a TV crime procedural with the life of a young man who by his surroundings is only perceived as the "Generic Asian Man" - he is an actor trying to get a role beyond that of a clichéd Asian person, but he is also forced into the role of "Generic Asian Man" in real life. The whole effect is surreal and brilliantly conveying the strange loops in which a person who is reduced to a stereotype is trapped - certainly, the whole TV/actor part of the book can also be read as strictly metaphorical. Yu cleverly plays out his ideas by writing parts of the book in the form of a movie script, and the whole novel is typed in Courier (the font used in scripts).

The protagonist, Willis Wu, is perpetually living in an "Interior Chinatown", a prison of perceptions in which he is trapped - and he is not even Chinese, he is, like the author, of Taiwanese descent (the point of course being that all of Asia is frequently seen as monolithic). While Wu works hard and has the ambition to make something of himself, his range of paragons is limited by what Western society allows him to be, and breaking free of his role of "Generic Asian Man" to become "Kung Fu Guy" only means to conform to another stereotype - what is he to do to break the mold in an averse environment? How can he find himself, find happiness?

Apart from giving us Wu's perspective in interior monologue, Yu reflects contemporary American society and its cultural projections by inventing storylines for the police procedural "Black and White", featuring a clichéd woman and a clichéd black man who play the detectives - you get the idea: One is black and one is white, but the series also paints reality in black and white. Where is the Asian representation, what is Wu's role? And how do minorities, employed to project diversity, act towards each other? Yu's narration breaks down the barrier between reality and the fictional series within the novel, and everyone is forced to act constantly, cast in a movie they never volunteered to be in.

Now all of this is brilliantly thought out and highly inventive, but as the storyline is sparse and many parts are highly descriptive, clearly stating narrative puposes and sometimes even bordering on essay writing, the basic idea did not really carry over the whole distance (although the book only has 288 pages). While the repetitiveness is part of the whole point (see: strange loops), it certainly does not help the pacing of the text. But to be fair, this criticism also touches upon the field of personal taste, and I'm sure that many other readers won't mind the points I just addressed.

All in all, Charles Yu wrote a daring, innovative, intelligent book with an important message, and while I wasn't fully immersed in the text, this novel is certainly worth checking out.”; Meike. - In: Goodreads, 19.11.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3141080672> [08.06.2023]

"Although it took me a few chapters to understand the shift between second person narration and third person as well as understanding why most of the book was in the form of a movie script, once I understood, it was a very personal way to explore pop culture, racial stereotypes and trying to break free of the role each of us is supposed to play. In this story a young Chinese man strive to do more than work in a Chinese restaurant and play minor roles in TV shows and movies. This was a book that made me think. Its also a book worthy of a second reading to understand the multiple layers of the story being told.”; Nelda Brangwin. - In: Goodreads, 14.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3142187505> [08.06.2023]

"Reading this book felt like a refreshing and rare adventure. The author seamlessly takes the readers "off" and "on" screen. At some point, I can't tell whether I'm reading the "real" stories or the "TV/movie script", and I think that is the intended effect. Overall, I think the book does a great job highlighting the many issues that Asian Americans are facing, from the lack of representation in the media to the struggle to be accepted as "Americans"."; Epickkasten. - In: Goodreads, 15.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3143471800> [08.06.2023]

"Heartfelt & wildly creative.

(And also quick to read, since the whole thing is set up like a script.)

What a weird & great way to talk about race & family & identity & pop culture.”; Christy. - In: Goodreads, 15.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3089534711> [08.06.2023]

"At first I thought this book was headed in a problematic direction until it got to the end and showed its real perspective. What a great book about Asian American identity.”; Katy. - In: Goodreads, 19.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3145983197> [08.06.2023]

"I really enjoyed this examination of racial identity and the “model minority” myth and how challenging it can be for Asian people to grapple with who they are authentically versus who they think they are under the white gaze. The format was really interesting and made it a quick but thought provoking read."; Katie. - In: Goodreads, 21.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2934240470> [08.06.2023]

"Complex and sad. I recommend reading Interior Chinatown."; eveltrain. - In: Goodreads, 26.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3135007706> [08.06.2023]

"QUICK TAKE: funny, emotional, thought-provoking satire about Willis, a “Generic Asian man” who plays a background extra on the TV procedural Black & White, but dreams of one day being “Kung Fu Guy”, the most respected role that anyone who looks like him can attain. The book is extremely funny and heartfelt and explores racial stereotypes and pop culture through a satirical lens in a clever and extremely unique way. Easily one of my favorite books of the year."; Jordan (Jordy’s Book Club). - In: Goodreads, 04.12.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3160678485> [08.06.2023]

"This book is brilliant. It shows what you can do when you write with perception, humor and creativity about something you have experienced and understand intimately. No cultural appropriation here. He’s also one of the writers on the HBO series West World, so he understands TV too. The book tells the story of Willis Wu and his Chinese American family. Their story is interwoven inventively with the description of the generic roles that the Wu’s and other residents of their SRO play in a TV series. The roles range from Generic Asian Man #1, to Special Guest Star, to Recurring and (if you are really lucky) to Kung Fu Guy. Once you reach Kung Fu Guy, you hit a ceiling. It’s virtually impossible to make it to Generic Man. Willis meets Ethnically Ambiguous Girl who “gets to be objectified by men of all races”. The characters are on the sidelines in a society that lumps all Asians together, and never wanted them here. I loved this book. I’d read more by this author in a heartbeat."; Faith. - In: Goodreads, 29.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2969344664> [08.06.2023]

"Told in the form of a script, this book was original, sarcastic & provocative. It played on the stereotype that "All Asian men look the same" in a vert interesting way.

The fact that the main character was part of a show was confusing at times, but I found this book to be very clever overall. All the "moving" sections were left at the end, though."; Ylenia. - In: Goodreads, 31.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3016741496> [08.06.2023]

"It's probably been forty years since I read a book that managed to be both a book of ideas and a book of fun. Willis spends most of his life living in a soundstage

for a police procedural. He is often Generic Asian Man but dreams of being Kung Fu Guy. Except for the trial scene, most of the best moments take place outside the soundstage, but you'll have to read it; no spoilers here."; Mary Bellamy. - In: Goodreads, 02.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3168399733> [08.06.2023]

"DNF. I was very interested in reading this book due to reviews and buzz, BUT... I read about half and was just not compelled to finish. I thought it too clever by half. Willingly abandoned."; Andrea. - In: Goodreads, 31.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3166493945> [08.06.2023]

"4.5 *

Loved it! Creative, funny as hell and educational. The framing and format are amazing. And the message, unmistakable. I am thrilled to have experienced this book. Highly recommended!

Listen to the audiobook. The performance is creatively designed, superbly executed and adds so much nuance and meaning to this wonderful book.

I was ROFLMAO for much of the book. Nothing cuts thru societal bullshit like laughter. Will begin rereading it tomorrow; so possibly more comments later..."; Cheryl. - In: Goodreads, 01.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3168661488> [08.06.2023]

"This novel is about what it's like to be not just a model minority, but an invisible minority, or as the book jacket describes it, "a bit player in your own life." Willis Wu is Generic Asian Man, son of Old Asian Man and Old Asian Woman, but he aspires to be Kung Fu Guy, which to him is the pinnacle of success. The book itself is high-concept; it's written as a teleplay of a police procedural called Black and White, but the existence of the show is a metaphor that keeps bleeding over into Willis's real life. There are achingly sad passages -- as in the death of Old Fong, who after an old age of knowing that there was one person who cared for him no matter what, died wondering if that were true -- and also hilarious ones as when Older Brother, defending Willis for the criminal disappearance of himself (yeah, this book is just like that), objects on the grounds that, "It's way too sexy in here." This book is beautiful and brilliant, but also confusing."; Rachel. - In: Goodreads, 01.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3170948618> [08.06.2023]

***edit** NATIONAL BOOK AWARD WINNER!!!! YAYAY

I LOVED this book!! I'm in awe of the format. I think it's incredibly creative! I hope people read it. I keep recommending it at work....

Willis Wu is an actor, yet he doesn't even see himself as one in life, nor as the protagonist of his own life. He's type-casted and stereotyped into roles. The author Charles Yu exposes the truth about Asians in Hollywood and the lack of variety in work

that is offered to them in Interior Chinatown. Asian men are forced to play OLD ASIAN MAN or GENERIC ASIAN MAN, while women are PRETTY ORIENTAL WOMAN OR OLD ASIAN WOMAN. Yu’s character Willis Wu works on a set for a police procedural or Law and Order type cop investigative show, as a generic Asian man.

Anytime an Asian character, whether it be OLD ASIAN MAN, GENERIC ASIAN MAN, or ORIENTAL #1 in the script, he is non-essential. They exist on the side lines, just a person to bounce words off to. Charles Yu purposefully includes this dialogue and text on the margins of the book to provide a visual representation for the reader, thus showing how the Asian characters are still in the background and at the margins of their careers, even in this story.

The author’s frankness in exposing and highlighting this common problem in Hollywood is worth reading alone. I highly recommend!"; Kristina. - In: Goodreads, 19.11.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3156560689> [08.06.2023]

"I think I’m probably the target audience that Yu was writing for. He set his allegorical story in a generic Chinatown populated by generic Chinese people. I pictured Grant Street in San Francisco because that’s what I know but given the broadcast element, it’s probably Los Angeles. He is giving voice to frustration at being lost in the sea of “generic Asian men,” features blurred together in flat faces and slant eyes.

And as the book progresses, he dishes out injustices Chinese have experienced in their 200 years in America, though I found his tie-in with Blacks not all that convincing, but you can’t ignore that they’re both been treated for how they look. Willis Wu is eminently likable and I was sympathetic to his struggle to be successful in his broadcast field. I realized pretty quickly that I was reading a fable/fantasy but wasn’t surprised when Yu braided in the more meaty issues.

We have enjoyed Chinatown as a novelty and always stopped in to shop and eat when we were there. He concludes his books with this quote: “Chinatown, like the phoenix, rose from the ashes with a new facade, dreamed up by an American-born Chinese man, built by white architects, looking like a stage-set China that does not exist.” Ouch, and guilty."; Sharon - In: Goodreads, 15.03.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3169924151> [08.06.2023]

"This was definitely a “different” reading experience for me, one that was filled with playful jabs at Hollywood and the stereotypes that are so prevalently applied to Asians in modern society. Written in the form of a TV show script (complete with Courier font and everything!), the story revolves around a protagonist named Willis Wu - who, after playing various minor and often non-speaking roles such as Silent Henchman and Dead Asian Guy, has finally worked his way up to the role of Generic Asian Man in a TV show starring Black and White (a black male cop and white

female cop, respectively). Though Willis eventually makes his way up to Very Special Guest Star -- the pinnacle of success for most Asians in the Chinatown SRO where he lives - Willis aims to follow in the footsteps of Older Brother before him and attain the highest level role that all Asian males aspire to: the role of Kung Fu Guy. As he continually climbs the ladder in the hopes of eventually finding his place in the spotlight, Willis makes many surprising (and not so surprising) discoveries along the way, both about his family as well as the Chinatown he grew up in. Throughout this journey, as Willis hops from one role to another, he begins to realize that the roles he is resigned to playing are not necessarily aligned with the roles he “wants” to play. The question then becomes whether Willis will be able to break out of the Generic Asian Man role he seems “destined” to play and instead follow his own path, even if it completely upends the reality he has believed his entire life.

It’s rare for me to come across a book quite like this one - a book that is funny, smart, innovative, daring, playful, yet at the same time, also deep and thought-provoking. I love how the author Charles Yu was able to take his personal experiences as an Asian male in American society and transform it into a social commentary of sorts, satirically poking fun at various cultural stereotypes, but in a way that is good-natured and respectful. A book like this one only works if it is written by someone who knows the subject matter intimately, and even then, it can be risky due to how differently each person experiences the world around them. For me, growing up as an Asian-American in a neighborhood where there weren’t many people who looked like me, I could wholeheartedly relate to a lot of what the story’s main characters - especially Willis - went through. Charles Yu was also spot-on where most of the cultural stereotypes were concerned - I found myself nodding my head in agreement throughout much of the story (and also laughing hysterically in the process).

This is one of those books that is very difficult to review because each person’s experience reading and reacting to it will be different depending on the place in society you’re from. I personally found this one clever, brilliant, and absolutely resonant on so many levels, but of course others who read this may not feel the same way. I would still recommend this book though...and who knows, I might even check out this author’s backlist at some point!

Received ARC from Pantheon Books (Random House) via Edelweiss.”; Bkwmlee.
- In: Goodreads, 04.02.2020. Available from:
<https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3087497982> [08.06.2023]

“A rare book where second person narration works. The premise is interesting, but overall it didn’t really capture me. Wasn’t a fan of the dialouge, but loved the scene and character descriptions.”; Máté. - In: Goodreads, 04.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3165938193> [08.06.2023]

“What a brilliantly innovative way to bring a new perspective on how mainstream America views the plight of Asian Americans for far too many decades. I’ll

admit- it took me a few chapters to get into the swing of it, based on the format... but once I was in, I was IN. This is one of those books that will make you question how you view those who are OTHER than you, as well as what reflection you cast upon the world around you. I'll say it again, for emphasis: BRILLIANT."; Kami Bumgardner. - In: Goodreads, 05.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3166265953> [08.06.2023]

"INT. CHINATOWN - DAY

Ever since you were a boy, you've been fascinated with Asian pop culture. Starting with films starring the Kung Fu Guy, you progress to classics, arthouse and eventual became a festival fan. You recognise the tropes but go along with them because there's nothing else available. Cut to: 2020. Charles Yu releases a clever novel that dissects your assumptions while playing to your love of pop culture.

DISSOLVE TO:

INTERIOR CHINATOWN is not your average book. This is something you might expect from the author of *How to Live Safely in a Science Fictional Universe*, which contains a book-within-a-book the lead obtained from his future self. Here Yu uses the conventions of the screenplay to explore how Asians are homogenously presented in Hollywood media.

Fuelled by his experience on television shows like HBO's *Westworld* and FX's *Legion*, Yu takes the marginalisation of Asian characters as a starting point for his story. Willis Wu, or as he's more frequently referred to Generic Asian Man, is stuck playing background roles. This is not just true of Willis the character, as much of his life is depicted in the form of a screenplay where he is literally relegated a Generic Asian role. He aspires, of course, for the leading part of the Kung Fu Guy.

There's two things that can turn into gimmicks really quickly: non-traditional prose forms and the 'second person' point of view. Yu uses both liberally: the whole thing is presented in the Courier font synonymous with scripts, and it switches between the second- and third-person narrative, as if the former were notes from Central Casting.

Yet INTERIOR CHINATOWN is funny. Not just funny but sharply satirical as well, careening in and out of weird cutaways, moments from a cop show (called *Black and White* after the ethnicity of its cast) and key fragments from Wu's life. These maintain the screenplay format, although Yu uses longer descriptive passages to get into these vignettes.

Is the text a little repetitive at times? Perhaps a little, although having different Asian men from completely different countries living in a single room occupancy (or SRO) It all culminates in - yet even this plays into the expected conventions of the genre, doubling down on Yu's point. Everyday microaggressions are

part of the script of Asian American daily life. It all culminates in a grand courtroom scene, complete with speeches, the kind that seem to always solve historic racism on screen.

Even if you think you're pretty woke, Yu cleverly weaves in historical and contemporary examples of how we continue to support this system. My wake-up moment was a quote Yu highlights from Erving Goffman: "When...an outsider happens upon a performance that was not meant for him... the performers will find themselves temporarily torn between two possible realities." As someone who has Asia in Focus on my film site, it's a line that forced me to take a beat and check for context as an outsider.

In fact, INTERIOR CHINATOWN asks us to challenge the very fabric of the American creation myth, one where Asian involvement is often left out because it's too challenging to fit the accepted narrative. For every Crazy Rich Asians or The Farewell, there's still scores of other films that exhibit Yu's exemplars of typecasting on and off screen. If Yu's book helps us recognise and reject these offerings, then satire like this might not be as cutting."; Richard Gray. - In: Goodreads, 05.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3174629701> [08.06.2023]

"Willis Wu is Generic Asian Man, or sometimes Delivery Guy or Dead Asian Guy. His lifelong dream has been to attain the role of Kung Fu Guy, the highest rank available to an Asian actor. Willis, his aging parents, and all their Chinatown neighbors work at the Golden Palace restaurant, which serves as an interior on the cop show Black and White. In the world of this story, there is no reality beyond the show, or at least Willis can't conceive of any bigger dream than playing a stereotyped other in the dichotomy of Black and White.

INTERIOR CHINATOWN (or, INTERIOR: CHINATOWN) is another great, weird work of metaphorical metafiction from Yu. Since Willis exists inside a TV world, the novel is laid out in the font and format of a screenplay, with longer prose sections mixed in among the centered dialogue. Rather than becoming a tedious gimmick, the format grows even more clever as the story proceeds and Willis strains against the limitations of his life. This novel is funny and heart-wrenching by turns, and it's packed with sharp observations on race in America. I recommend it, and I guarantee you've never read anything quite like it."; Lisa Eckstein. - In: Goodreads, 05.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2962573834> [08.06.2023]

"Reviews indicated it was humorous book. I didn't connect with its humor."; Kim T. Otto. - In: Goodreads, 05.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3177366710> [08.06.2020]

"This was an extremely creative novel that balances the rigors of racial prejudice with the comedy of an invented detective drama script. The idea to portray a range of identity with the hierarchy of roles in a cast was executed flawlessly,

providing a playful structure for the ruminations discussed. Filled with illustrious montages, scripty banter, and a surreal narrative, this book hits you hard in the feelings but brightens it up with perfect stage lighting and execution. I really enjoyed such a unique display of talent! What a neat read!"; Jorie. - In: Goodreads, 06.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3171220031> [08.06.2023]

"Started & finished on a rainy day swept along by a fierce audio performance of this brilliant, heartbreaking & heart healing, funny, surreal book written in teleplay style. Unique, acidic and mesmerizing, this painfully truthful and authentic story goes beyond "Hollywood tropes" to reveal commonalities shared by us all in dealing with family, aging, love, parenting and dream-chasing."; Lisa. - In: Goodreads, 06.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3177841676> [08.06.2023]

"4.5 Stars

This is the first Wu that I have read. I can tell you that it will not be my last. It is formatted in a unique manner. I am a sucker for people that use unique ways to tell a story. It took me a little bit to get pulled into the story (which is why I docked it .5 star), perhaps because of it's format, but once I got pulled in, that was part of it's charm. I was alerted to this novel by someone I follow on Instagram (thanks Jordy #jordymademedoit). I look forward to more recommendations from him, and others I follow in the book sphere on IG!!"; ScottK. - In: Goodreads, 07.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3169604204> [08.06.2023]

***winner of 2020 National Book Awards for Fiction!

This is it. The root of it all. The real history of yellow people in America. Two hundred years of being perpetual foreigners. – Charles Yu, interior Chinatown

One of my most anticipated books of winter 2020 and sure to be one of my top favorites of the year, Charles Yu's "Interior Chinatown" was a truly unique reading experience. Hilarious, inventive, and smart literary novel about a Generic Asian Man who dreams of being a Kung Fu Guy, set in generic Chinatown, populated by generic Chinese (along with few other Generic Asians) people. Reminiscent of Booker Prize-winning novel, "The Sellout" by Paul Beatty, it's deceptively entertaining & funny on the surface.

"You're here, supposedly, in a new land full of opportunity, but somehow have gotten trapped in a pretend version of the old country."

Combining Yu's talents as a screenwriter & a writer, the novel is written like a movie script, divided into seven distinct "acts." Although I don't typically like experimental formats, and it was definitely a risk, it worked brilliantly for this story. The novel centers around William Wu, a "Generic Asian Man" living in Chinatown SRO and working in Golden Palace restaurant, located beneath the same building,

dreaming of being a “Kung Fu Guy,” the most coveted role a “Generic Asian Man” can attain. William also has minor roles as all the generic asian characters you can think of in a procedural cop show that takes place in the restaurant & Chinatown. This is where his reality & tv show blurs as he struggles to free himself from the confinement of the stereotypical social roles assigned to the “Generic Asian Man.” While the book centers around William’s life, Yu broadens the narrative as the story progresses with detailing of life among Asian Americans living as so-called foreigners, history of injustices against immigrants in the West for centuries, Asian experiences in America, and Chinese culture, customs, and family dynamics.

“Look where we are. Look what you made yourself into. Working your way up the system doesn’t mean you beat the system. It strengthens it. It’s what the system depends on.”

Although it’s categorized as literary, it’s a genre-defying novel, and in a slim volume, Yu manages to create a sweeping picture of Asian American experiences in America. Characters are so well-developed, you can keenly feel their pain, struggles, and emotions. They struggle to find a sense of place & identity amid a complex & traumatic history of oppression, displacement, and feeling of marginalization and invisible in the setting they find themselves in. Yu handles important, eye-opening, and thought-provoking issues of race, stereotypes, and immigration in a playful yet heartfelt manner that blew me away! The writing is so simple, yet masterful – style & prose, characters, setting, history, structure, all worked out perfectly. I highlighted so many paragraphs in this book. It’s fast-paced with sense of urgency, and Yu covered so much, it’s amazing what he has accomplished in a book that is less than 300 pages. With its biting satirical commentary on race, stereotype, pop culture, immigration, and assimilation, not only it’s entertaining, it’s illuminating, an essential, heartbreaking, thought-provoking read. Highly recommend it! 🧐👉 📖"; Monica Kim | Musings of Monica. - In: Goodreads, 19.11.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3165365871> [08.06.2023]

"Yu offers a glimpse at the Asian American experience in a wholly unique way that absolutely kept me captivated throughout this short novel."; Danielle. - In: Goodreads, 07.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3177270538> [08.06.2023]

"Probably one of the most ingeniously conceived books about the immigrant experience, Charles Yu, a television writer for such shows as ‘Westworld’ and ‘Legion’ spins the story of Willis Wu, a young actor growing up in Los Angeles who dreams of moving up the ranks from Background Oriental Male to the ultimate pinnacle: Kung Fu Guy. Yu constructs his story with a brilliant combination of prose and script, including such small terrific details like the typewriter typeface the book is written in.

He moves with ease from hilarious satire (Willis stuck in a seemingly endless loop of appearing on the macho cop drama, “Black & White”) to ultimately a stirring

manifesto about identity, race, immigration and what it means to be an American. It's a smart, funny, and moving book which holds particular relevance today in our fractured United States."; Brett Benner. - In: Goodreads, 07.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3178171211> [08.06.2023]

"I've previously read all 3 of Yu's earlier books, and while I enjoyed them I always felt that he's much much smarter than me and therefore I probably didn't really catch all of the different layers of his storytelling.

This book I found to be much more accessible, a wonderful satire on race, roles and identity in Hollywood (and life) - which makes sense given that the likely reason he hasn't put out a book in awhile is due to his work writing for the HBO show Westworld."; Matthew Holley. - In: Goodreads, 08.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3172081296> [08.06.2023]

"Forgot what drew me to book but I'm aware of Yu's other work (haven't read them). This sounded like a weird but intriguing premise: a discussion of race, politics, stereotypes (on race, in entertainment, etc.) in a book written like a movie script. It sounds like it could really work and it also sounds rather risky and a setup for disaster.

Luckily, it works. It probably helps Yu is an actual screenwriter and so understand that format. 'Interior' takes us through the times of Generic Asian Man, a guy who lives in Chinatown, works on a cop show (not unlike 'Law & Order') where he's a background extra-type (hence, Generic Asian Man). But understandably, he wants more than that and finds he's got a shot at maybe opening some doors.

The story isn't "traditional" with a beginning, middle, end with a conflict to resolve. Yu peppers the script/text with lots of stories of what it's like to be GAM, from family history to dealing to what it's like being Asian in a country like the United States, his relationships, etc.

A lot of it is really incisive commentary that made me wince, chuckle, raise my eyebrow, etc. If you think about the tropes and stereotypes that are often overused in Hollywood, this can hit home pretty hard. And if you're familiar with some of the stories of Chinese immigrants and their children, this might resonate a lot.

Overall, I thought it worked, despite my initial skepticism when I began reading. And I'll agree: I can understand why people didn't really care for this, didn't think the script "style" worked and there have been times where I have been in that camp. But I do think Yu really does have some good things to say that's worth thinking about. At the same time, there are times when the book drags and/or the text really isn't that interesting.

So I'd say the book is really a 3.5 but I thought the framework of a script was pretty cool so I'm bumping this to 4. Borrowed from the library and think that's probably best but I wouldn't have regretted waiting till I bought it in paperback,

either. I might check out his other books, too.”; Bookworm. - In: Goodreads, 08.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3177030052> [08.06.2023]

“An incredibly creative, self-aware book that I read in one sitting.”; Brittany Baker. - In: Goodreads, 25.02.2021. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3037812889> [08.06.2023]

“This book was brilliant and witty, taking on a new narrative form through a script-style allegory where Yu addresses cultural stereotypes, pitfalls, and Asian representation in American culture.

Ultimately, this book is one you will love or hate. The creative formatting, and style are not for everyone. If you go into this book thinking you're going to have a normal narrative experience, you will automatically find yourself disappointed. Instead, sit back, relax and enjoy the ride. Charles Yu has carved out an interesting format that seemed almost too perfect for the racial issues he was seeking to address. Surprisingly excellent and well executed.”; Madeleine Moss. - In: Goodreads, 16.03.2021. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3163713909> [08.06.2023]

“Dave Eggers eat your fucking heart out

ACTUAL NETGALLEY REVIEW

I LOVED How to Live Safely in a Science Fictional Universe and Charles Yu did not disappoint with Interior Chinatown. This book is a master class on minimalist writing for maximum emotional effect. It's Your Fathers, Where Are They? And the Prophets, Do They Live Forever? if that book was half as good as the author thought it was. It's beautiful and thoughtful and offers valuable critique of representation in media and EVERYONE NEEDS TO READ IT.”; Taylor. - In: Goodreads, 11.11.2022. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3040967254> [08.06.2023]

Най-нови

“This book is weird and really confusing, but it manages to be quite insightful and even relatable, although I'm not an American-born Chinese or American or Chinese. I really like how the author articulates the experience of the main character. It's an important and tricky discussion, but the story makes its case well, especially in the climax, because I can see in that moment how the whole story kind of comes together. My main problem is I had no idea what was happening most of the way through. I don't know what is real and what is a movie script. Or maybe that is the point, and I can't tell because I'm too stupid. I might increase the rating once I sit on it for some time and deduce where all the metaphors are.”; Mint. - In: Goodreads,

06.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5591848081> [08.06.2023]

"The screenplay format of this novel is a clever way of presenting the theme of people of Asian descent feeling forced to "play roles" in American society. The device is also confusing since there seems to be a TV show being filmed as part of the plot. Are all of the characters actually working as actors, or is it all a metaphor, or some combination? The climactic scene has such a feeling of abstraction that I decided that I was meant to be disconcerted, and the blurry line between literal and metaphorical "acting" was intentional. The good news about the format is that it keeps the tone light in spite of some heavy concepts. The bad news is that the book doesn't have much of the qualities a reader generally enjoys in a novel (description, cohesive plot threads, character development). My enjoyment was 3 stars, but I'm giving it 4 for the unique and thought provoking approach."; Marie. - In: Goodreads, 06.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3924356037> [08.06.2023]

"Not my type of read."; Mary. - In: Goodreads, 06.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5598814492> [08.06.2023]

"super sick way of storytelling with the screenplay format. def was like wtf is going on what is real but by the end i'm like ok i see what he was doing in telling the story that way. after it all, def related to that feeling of performing and then being like who am i but also really cool look into what that experience is like for Yu as a chinese american.

the "why doesn't this face look american?" really got me. the conversation on otherness and it being similar but completely different to the black american experience, and how white americans view each experience but also how Yu views it... p cool

kind of reads like a memoir or even like a think piece which was really interesting and again, using the screenplay format was really cool. plus loved the backstory montages for willis' parents. muah love seeing parents as people and not just parents. and also love a quick read! wasn't sure if i was just enjoying it and speeding through or if it's truly a quick read but it def flew by. would def recommend"; Simone. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3825832407> [08.06.2023]

"4.5 stars

Yu writes about race with blunt honesty and humor. Such a unique reading experience. I listened on audio and highly recommend that format as the narrator was incredible. This book will make you uncomfortable and will challenge the way you think about race in this country."; Rachael. - In: Goodreads, 04.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3945114208> [08.06.2023]

"Finally got around to this book a few years late. Started it after dinner and literally didn't put it down. I've never read anything like this, it's so singular and creative and thought provoking. Loved it"; Sarah Barnett. - In: Goodreads, 04.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/4170869691> [08.06.2023]

"my only complaint is i kept getting lost but i think it's just bc i kept losing and re-renting the book bc otherwise it was brilliant"; Lauren. - In: Goodreads, 03.06.2023. Available from <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5593406949> [08.06.2023]

"As a film enthusiast alongside enjoying immersing in different cultural settings, this novel is superbly written.

Presented in a manner that mirrors a movie script, literally, the plot is compelling as it touches on upbringing, expectations, and amounting to something, or someone I shall say (read it to glean my reference)

Also the levity is sharp. Jokes are inputted at the perfect time, perfect place.

Do yourself and me, a favor, read this book."; Deepak Lal. - In: Goodreads, 03.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5592516812> [08.06.2023]

"This is one of the most unique and playfully written books I've ever read. It's extremely entertaining while also informative and deeply personal about the Asian American experience, the prejudices they faced/face. Written in the format of a screen-play, reading this felt similar to reading a graphic novel, I almost feel like I watched it. I really loved reading the "montage scenes" the most."; Britt. - In: Goodreads, 03.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5330420157> [08.06.2023]

"This was a thought provoking and innovative in its format. It's a story about Willis who is playing "Generic Asian man" but dreams of one day being "Kung Fu Guy" which is about as high as an Asian actor can aspire to. Through the experiences of Willis an an actor and the other Asian actors around him, we see the struggles with racism, glass ceilings and stereotypes that can easily translate to life outside of the stage as well. It also brings to light the financial ramifications of all of those struggles. In fact one of my favorite quotes from this book is "But the widest gulf in the world is the distance between getting by and not quite getting by" and all this is told while Willis is living in a SRO housing apartment. It's a slim volume but packs a punch. I listened to this on audiobook for most of it and it is wonderful on audio so I definitely recommend this in print and in audio."; Caroline (readtotheend on IG). - In: Goodreads, 02.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5591257234> [08.06.2023]

"Not a big fan of this. Felt a lot like an angry Reddit post, although at least the protagonist picks up on his internalized racism. It would be very hard to be friends with a guy like this."; Matthew Law. - In: Goodreads, 01.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5588922178> [08.06.2023]

"I am sorry to say that I did not like this book. Others in my book club did, but I didn't find much about it to enjoy.

Mr. Yu didn't make me like the characters at all. I did not like the format of reading a screenplay throughout most of the book.

While I sympathize with the plight of the Asian people in cinema and in life, I did not connect enough with Mr. Yu's characters to really care about them.

This made me feel bad about myself. I should have cared, but I didn't, so therefore I found no interest in this book. I don't mind a book that points out the failings of our society. Just don't make me dislike myself for not being able to empathize."; Beverley Albright. - In: Goodreads, 01.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5538757572> [08.06.2023]

"This is a difficult book to rate because I'm trying to balance my personal enjoyment and also the goal of the book into the rating I give.

There are some parts I really enjoyed, and there was a lot of warmth in the book. The level of confusion I experienced trying to determine what was real and what was not definitely made this book a pain to read at points because my brain does not like to not understand what is happening when I read. However, I know this was mostly the intent of the author.

This book was very thematic as opposed to being focused on a plot or developing a unique character. The author did a pretty good job with this, but I don't think it's necessarily the kind of book I would gravitate toward. It's not what I was expecting from this book going into it. In some ways, I was a bit disappointed by this; in other ways, I was pleasantly surprised. This is definitely a unique book.

Personally, I would give this book about 3.5 stars."; Jeremy Weitendorf. - In: Goodreads, 31.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5473410495> [08.06.2023]

"很喜欢作者用剧本构架模糊了现实和舞台界限的这种写法。从好莱坞华裔演员这个角度来讨论族群种族身份的老问题·旧瓶也有新酒。"; Yvette. - In: Goodreads, 24.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5570254651> [08.06.2023]

"3.5 stars

Willis Wu is an actor in a LA Cop Show called Black and White, because the main two detectives are a beautiful white woman and a ruggedly handsome Black man. Much of the show is set in Chinatown, at the Golden Palace Restaurant. Willis plays 'Generic Asian Man' but aspires to become 'Kung Fu Guy'.

Told in semi-screenplay format with dialogue, stage directions and descriptions of montages and flashbacks, the story is a fascinating look at race with regard to Asian stereotyping. For example, Willis was born in LA to 'Handsome Young Asian' and 'Beautiful Asian Restaurant Hostess' but is reprimanded by the show staff when he forgets to talk with a Chinese accent. His looks force him to forever be an outsider in his own city.

Willis finds love with Karen Lee, a mixed race woman who guest stars on the show, but then struggles when her career takes off while he still is struggling to be more than a bit part actor, doomed to be killed whenever he achieves special guest star status. In the case of death on the show, you are forced to sit out for a minimum of 45 days before re-entering as a bit part actor in the background because they figure no one will really notice you.

I enjoyed this novel, and the light it shines on historical prejudice against Chinese immigrants, which led to many laws like the Chinese Exclusion Act in the late 1800s, miniscule immigration quotas in the 1920s and prohibitions against owning property which forced asians into a virtual ghetto in the 'Chinatown' area of many cities. He also ruminates on the fact that although much discrimination occurred for both races, there is still residual animosity between Blacks and Asians."; Elise. - In: Goodreads, 20.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3233211766> [08.06.2023]

"This was such an interesting read; form and function complimented each other beautifully. It was impossible to tell where the tv show ends and Willis's life begins and I think that really added to the messages and themes explored, particularly that question of who gets to tell stories—both who gets to tell stories in popular culture and who we allow to tell our own individual story, which are two questions with heavy overlap. Willis's life sometimes being one and the same as the script for Black and White shows how Willis's story is being told by someone else. The second person aspect also emphasized that someone else was directing Willis's life. Because I listened to the audiobook, I didn't have the visual aid of formatting and I wonder how the formatting played into the blur (or if it helped delineate) between the script and Willis's life.

"You're alone. You got exactly what you wanted, didn't you? Or did they give it to you, the thing you thought you wanted? The role of a lifetime is one you can never bring yourself to quit. Karen was right—you are trapped. Doing well is the trap. A different kind, but still a trap. Because you're still in a show that doesn't have a role for you." (3:11)

I especially thought that “Act VI: The Case of the Missing Asian” was super clever. It’s a courtroom scene in which Willis is put on trial for disappearing or self-imprisonment. At one point, Willis asks if he’s the suspect or the victim and the judge says that’s what they’re there to determine. The adversarial nature of courtroom drama was a great frame for the way that minorities are pitted against each other and members pitted against themselves to distract from how whiteness defines their status in American society and allowed for the confusing complexities of these feelings and relationships to shine through when they obviously didn’t fit into the mold of a court case.

It was mentioned in some parts how all these Asian American children of immigrants study so hard and work so hard only to be typecast as Generic Asian Man/Woman, and even though it’s true that despite their hard work they still aren’t recognized as individuals, I wonder if saying that they are all academic high achievers undermines this point in some way? That’s a half-baked thought but curious if that resonates with anyone.

All together a super interesting and clever read, maybe more than 4 stars, 4.25? 4.5?”; sofia (sofiasaysyeah). - In: Goodreads, 19.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3998075818> [08.06.2023]

Общият брой на отзивите за книгата „Interior Chinatown ” в Goodreads е **7737**, като най-много коментари има на английски език (**7437**). Проследени са **47** коментара, от които **46** са на английски език и **1** на китайски език.

Коментари в LibraryThing

"Although it took me a few chapters to understand the shift between second person narration and third person as well as understanding why most of the book was in the form of a movie script, once I understood, it was a very personal way to explore pop culture, racial stereotypes and trying to break free of the role each of us is supposed to play. In this story a young Chinese man strive to do more than work in a Chinese restaurant and play minor roles in TV shows and movies. This was a book that made me think. Its also a book worthy of a second reading to understand the multiple layers of the story being told."; brangwinn. - In: LibraryThing, 14.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/177710971> [08.06.2023]

"Forgot what drew me to book but I'm aware of Yu's other work (haven't read them). This sounded like a weird but intriguing premise: a discussion of race, politics, stereotypes (on race, in entertainment, etc.) in a book written like a movie script. It sounds like it could really work and it also sounds rather risky and a setup for disaster.

Luckily, it works. It probably helps Yu is an actual screenwriter and so understand that format. 'Interior' takes us through the times of Generic Asian Man, a guy who lives in Chinatown, works on a cop show (not unlike 'Law & Order') where he's

a background extra-type (hence, Generic Asian Man). But understandably, he wants more than that and finds he's got a shot at maybe opening some doors.

The story isn't "traditional" with a beginning, middle, end with a conflict to resolve. Yu peppers the script/text with lots of stories of what it's like to be GAM, from family history to dealing to what it's like being Asian in a country like the United States, his relationships, etc.

A lot of it is really incisive commentary that made me wince, chuckle, raise my eyebrow, etc. If you think about the tropes and stereotypes that are often overused in Hollywood, this can hit home pretty hard. And if you're familiar with some of the stories of Chinese immigrants and their children, this might resonate a lot.

Overall, I thought it worked, despite my initial skepticism when I began reading. And I'll agree: I can understand why people didn't really care for this, didn't think the script "style" worked and there have been times where I have been in that camp. But I do think Yu really does have some good things to say that's worth thinking about. At the same time, there are times when the book drags and/or the text really isn't that interesting.

So I'd say the book is really a 3.5 but I thought the framework of a script was pretty cool so I'm bumping this to 4. Borrowed from the library and think that's probably best but I wouldn't have regretted waiting till I bought it in paperback, either. I might check out his other books, too."; HoldMyBook. - In: LibraryThing, 08.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/178525162> [08.06.2023]

"This meta, metaphorical, and satirical gimmick of a book bored me with its heavy-handed points about the Chinese American experience, valid as they are. A mash-up of a novel and a screenplay, it reads quickly enough, but still feels like the ultimate overlong Saturday Night Live sketch. I never connected with the surface humor or underlying drama, leaving me only with a "I see what he's doing there" feeling as it built toward its big and deliberately cheesy courtroom finale."; villemzebrown. - In: LibraryThing, 22.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/180302602> [08.06.2023]

"Many rave reviews made me impatient to read this book. And now I have read it. So difficult to describe....written in the format of a screenplay, it moves back and forth in time, history, and various realities, which takes concentration to keep it all organized - is this the screenplay? is this a narrative? autobiographical? past/present, or ? The author does a great job of presenting stereotypical roles that Asians have experienced and still do experience in the United States. He blames Hollywood for contributing to the stereotypes, and also points fingers at Asians for furthering their own problems. At the same time, the book acknowledges how difficult it is to become a person first, without the "negative" aspects of Asian ethnicity he describes. I didn't

think this was a funny book, as others did. It was sad and a bit dark, and depressing at times. My library version is labeled as "science fiction" but I thought that was a stretch. Similar to saying *The Sound and The Fury* is science fiction. I think this novel is a commentary on racism that would be an excellent addition to a high school or college syllabus, and would provide material for a stimulating discussion.”; PhyllisReads. - In: LibraryThing, 23.08.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/188443197> [08.06.2023]

"Interior Chinatown didn't rock my world. One of the ways that the author describes racism against people of Asian descent is to describe the characters in terms of stereotypical movie/TV roles they could get at different stages of life. That was interesting, but sometimes confusing (at least in audio). In addition, the author injects long lists accounting horrible legislation, which were interesting, but weird in the context of a fictional story.”; joyblue. - In: LibraryThing, 28.08.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/182563063> [08.06.2023]

"This year's National Book Award Winner was an unusually structured novel which told the narrative of Willis Wu who struggles to become something more than the Ordinary Asian bit actor in the popular show called *Black and White*. The story is written as a screen play, setting the scenes as if providing the actors with background and direction. It's an original idea and one that obviously captured the attention of the judges for this year's prize . Throughout the story the readers are provided a detailed look at the forgettable life of the Asian American, cast into roles where if they are killed off in a script, they need to wait the formulated 45 days, death days, before they can return to another role.

"I know, Will. I know. I wish it didn't have to be like this, but you know how it is. You're an Asian Man. Your story was great, while it lasted, but now it's done. I hope our paths cross again. Maybe somewhere else."

Yu does manage to provide a great portrait of the Wu family, his parent's immigration, his brother's success, and his relationship with a another actress who can pass for bit parts as a representative of many countries:

"You're like a magical creature. A chameleon." "Able to pass in any situation as may be required," she says. "I get it all. Brazilian, Filipina, Mediterranean, Eurasian. Or just a really tan White girl with exotic-looking eyes. Everywhere I go, people think I'm one of them. They want to claim me for their tribe." "Must be amazing." "Yeah, I mean, I can be objectified by men of all races."

His parents have gotten older and the once great Kung Fu master, his father Sifu, is now reduced to working in the restaurant at the ground floor of the SRO apartments where his family lives. "Sifu had gotten this old without anyone noticing. Including your mother—deemed to have aged out of Asian Seductress, no longer Girl

with the Almond Eyes, now Old Asian Woman—living down the hall, their marriage having entered its own dusky phase, bound for eternity but separate in life."

On karaoke nights, (one of my favorite scenes) his father sings John Denver's Country Roads: "by the time he's done, you might understand why a seventy-seven-year-old guy from a tiny island in the Taiwan Strait who's been in a foreign country for two-thirds of his life can nail a song, note perfect, about wanting to go home."

I have to admit that by summarizing the novel and reflecting on the lines I highlighted, I liked the book even more. I would be interested in reading some of his earlier work and find out about his ideas in his contribution to the HBO show Westworld.

Lines:

Sifu had gotten this old without anyone noticing. Including your mother—deemed to have aged out of Asian Seductress, no longer Girl with the Almond Eyes, now Old Asian Woman—living down the hall, their marriage having entered its own dusky phase, bound for eternity but separate in life.

Bruce Lee proved too much. He was a living, breathing video game boss-level, a human cheat code, an idealized avatar of Asian-ness and awesomeness permanently set on Expert difficulty. Not a man so much as a personification, not a mortal so much as a deity on loan to you and your kind for a fixed period of time. A flame that burned for all yellow to understand, however briefly, what perfection was like.

There's just something about Asians that makes reality a little too real, overcomplicates the clarity, the duality, the clean elegance of BLACK and WHITE, the proven template and so the decision is made not in some overarching conspiracy to exclude Asians but because it's just easier to keep it how we have it.

MILES TURNER, 33. Tall and built. Really built. Like, if-gray-T-shirts-hadn't-been-invented-already-they-would-have-to-be-invented-just-so-Miles-could-wear-the-shit-out-of-them built. That kind of built.

by the time he's done, you might understand why a seventy-seven-year-old guy from a tiny island in the Taiwan Strait who's been in a foreign country for two-thirds of his life can nail a song, note perfect, about wanting to go home.

I know, Will. I know. I wish it didn't have to be like this, but you know how it is. You're an Asian Man. Your story was great, while it lasted, but now it's done. I hope our paths cross again. Maybe somewhere else.

There are a few years when you make almost all of your important memories. And then you spend the next few decades reliving them.

The words coming out of your mouth, you can feel it happening, how you're softening, changing into a different person. You were a bit player in the world of

Black and White, but here and now, in her world, you're more. Not the star of the show, something better. The star's dad. Somehow you were lucky enough to end up in her story.

That despite all of that, you somehow feel that your oppression, because it does not include the original American sin—of slavery—that it will never add up to something equivalent.

He is guilty, Your Honor, and ladies and gentlemen of the jury. Guilty of wanting to be part of something that never wanted him.

We're trapped as guest stars in a small ghetto on a very special episode. Minor characters locked into a story that doesn't quite know what to do with us. After two centuries here, why are we still not Americans? Why do we keep falling out of the story?"; novelcommentary. - In: LibraryThing, 25.11.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/192508519> [08.06.2023]

"Willis Wu has always been Generic Asian Man in the set happening in interior Chinatown, the cop drama Black and White constantly in production. He dreams of moving to bit parts in the shadow to becoming Kung Fu Guy, the highest attainable job for him, but it becomes more and more difficult for him to fit into this narrative.

Playfully using the format of a screenplay and making the reader work to tease out reality and the "show", Yu shows how racism in America has made Asian Americans - Chinese, Japanese, Taiwanese, and more - a generic "other", and how that could play out when internalized. The screenplay really cleverly makes you realize how ridiculous our stereotypical roles in movies have played out to give us a generic Asian man or exotic Asian woman, instead of recognizing the wide variety of experiences and personalities of individuals. It's a fast read and incredibly thought-provoking. I have a hunch I would get even more out of it on a reread."; bell7. - In: LibraryThing, 06.02.2021. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/196010028> [08.06.2023]

"Mostly written in the format of a screenplay, you play the role of Generic Asian Man in the cop show "Black and White," but you aspire to a bigger role, that of Kung Fu Guy. With hard work and practice, you eventually make it to Special Guest Star. The role of your lifetime is on the horizon but is it really in your reach? Asian stereotypes and tropes get a critical scrutiny and skewering, countered by tenderness and common humanity. There is a surreal quality to the reading experience--the protagonist is playing a TV role but is also trapped by roles in real life. What is real and how do we define ourselves?"; Salsabarian. - In: LibraryThing, 18.01.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/210554434> [08.06.2023]

"“Interior Chinatown” uses both a screenplay format and novel/narration format to tell the tale of Willis Wu, the "Generic Asian Man" who is stuck playing "Background Oriental Male" or "Delivery Guy" in the police “Black and White” (B&W)

series. But above all, he wants to become "Kung Fu Guy", a Bruce Lee, on screens everywhere. In the novel portions (or just lots of screenplay info), we learn about his upbringing, his parents, his desires and dilemmas, his relationships or lack thereof, and ultimately his decisions. Is being the "Kung Fu Guy" all that it's cracked up to be?

From the book:

"To be yellow in America. A special guest star, forever the guest."

"...Try to project: Responsible, Harmless. An unthreatening amount of color sprinkled in. That's the dream, a dream of blending in. A dream of going from Generic Asian Man to just plain Generic Man. To settle down. To stay here..."

These two quotes are the vibe of the book, summarizing the frustrations of being Asian in the US (and frankly, many parts of the world), especially a generation or two ago.

It hasn't been easy to find the words to review this book. At times, its analogies hit too close to home - the typical wishing more, better, or even different for oneself and the children. At other times, the sharp stereotyping comes across as insulting instead of illustrating. Or, analogies within the B&W becomes convoluted, removing the feelings of realism, and the story would momentarily fall into the Yu-lost-me abyss (sorry, bad pun). I put the book down many times, as I processed what my life could have been like if moments in time had gone differently (not that I ever had any aspirations to be a Kung Fu Guy). I know that the characters' conflicted emotions, the SRO housing situation, and the desire to get-out of Chinatown are very real. The B&W screenplay portions provide an opportunity to address the relationship of Chinese/Chinatown with respect to the Blacks and to the Whites. Other than the colors of a police car, the characters are literally a Black male cop and a White female cop - a hierarchy amongst the ethnicities and amongst the sexes.

I don't recommend this book for everyone. I feel that I can better understand what Yu is saying because of my own background. I understood the messages, I appreciated the light-handed approach in discussing many heavy subjects, but the trade-off is that it lacks gravitas. If the two quotes above trigger emotions and/or understanding, then enjoy!

More quotes:

On Disappointment:

"Old Asian Man looks at you, a look of disappointment flickering across his features with each accented word. You playing this part, talking like a foreigner. The son who was born here, raised here, a stranger to his own dad for what. For this. So he could be part of this, part of the American show, black and white, no part for yellow. The son who got As in every subject, including English, now making a living as Generic Asian Man."

On Stereotype:

“...At the moment he’s not Fong. He is Chinatown Mini Boss. Medium fish in a small pond. The guy before the guy. Intermediate obstacle. An act two villain who gets you into act three. It’s a good gig, even if Fong is starting to get typecast. Something about how gentle he is, they love to play off of that, love how his mild features, his slender build and slightly pasty complexion, make him the opposite of Turner, the opposite of masculine, make this Asian phenotype slightly and inherently creepy to the Western eye.”; varwenea. - In: LibraryThing, 02.05.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/208767570> [08.06.2023]

"Una riflessione sull'integrazione e sulla banalizzazione di una cultura, vissuta come viaggio nelle radici familiari. L'autore è sceneggiatore e usa appieno i suoi mezzi "cinematografici" per lavorare in modo originale sui piani del discorsi sugli stili e sul linguaggio. Bella scoperta."; d.v. - In: LibraryThing, 16.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/240534210> [08.06.2023]

В социалната мрежа LibraryThing книгата „Interior Chinatown” е получила общо **75** коментара. От тях **74** са на английски език и **1** на италиански език. Проследени са **11** коментара, публикувани през периода 2020-2023 г.

1.2. Коментари в български онлайн книжарници

Книгата „Interior Chinatown” не е достъпна в български онлайн книжарници.

Изводи:

Книгата „Interior Chinatown” има:

- Общо **58** проследени и отразени коментара в социалните мрежи
- **47** проследени коментара в социалната мрежа Goodreads, като **46** са на английски език и **1** на китайски език.
- **11** проследени коментара в социалната мрежа LibraryThing, от които **10** са на английски и **1** на италиански език, публикувани през периода 2019-2023 г.
- Книгата не е достъпна в български онлайн книжарници.

На база проучването във фаза 1 книгата „Interior Chinatown” се е осъществила като медия, заради наличието на голямо количество обратна връзка.

Дијаграма 1. Проследени коментари в социалните мрежи за периода 2020 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 2. Номинална (формална) обработка на книгата

Във втора фаза ще бъде проучено в кои чуждестранни и български дигитални каталози фигурира книгата „Interior Chinatown”. Ще бъдат изследвани и виртуални книготърговски каталози, в които може да е отразена книгата.

2.1. Дигитални каталози на библиотеки в чужбина

Brooklyn Public Library

<https://www.bklynlibrary.org/item?b=12244081>

Yu, Charles. Interior Chinatown. - New York : Pantheon Books, 2020. - 270 p.; 22 cm.

ISBN (13): 9780307907196

Beverly Hills Public Library

(<https://roxbury.beverlyhills.org/search/?searchtype=Y&searcharg=interior+chinatown&sortdropdown=&SORT=DZ&extended=0&SUBMIT=Search&searchlimits=&searchorgarg=Ytruly+madly+guilty%26SORT%3DDZ>)

Yu, Charles. Interior Chinatown. - New York : Pantheon Books, 2020. - 270 p.; 22 cm.

ISBN (13): 9780307907196

New York Public Library

(<https://nypl.na2.iiivega.com/search/card?id=ed093f06-f05c-54ef-b7e4-202dc3be5b1a&entityType=FormatGroup>)

Yu, Charles. Interior Chinatown. - New York : Pantheon Books, 2020. - 270 p.; 22 cm.

ISBN (13): 9780307907196

British Library

([https://explore.bl.uk/primo_library/libweb/action/display.do?tabs=moreTab&ct=display&fn=search&doc=BLL01020358566&indx=1&reclds=BLL01020358566&reclxs=0&elementId=0&renderMode=poppedOut&displayMode=full&frbrVersion=&frbg=&&scnt=0&scp.scps=scope%3A%28BLCCONTENT%29&tb=t&vid=BLVU1&mode=Basic&vl\(297891280UI0\)=any&srt=rank&tab=local_tab&dum=true&vl\(freeText0\)=interior%20chinatown&dstmp=1686071356699](https://explore.bl.uk/primo_library/libweb/action/display.do?tabs=moreTab&ct=display&fn=search&doc=BLL01020358566&indx=1&reclds=BLL01020358566&reclxs=0&elementId=0&renderMode=poppedOut&displayMode=full&frbrVersion=&frbg=&&scnt=0&scp.scps=scope%3A%28BLCCONTENT%29&tb=t&vid=BLVU1&mode=Basic&vl(297891280UI0)=any&srt=rank&tab=local_tab&dum=true&vl(freeText0)=interior%20chinatown&dstmp=1686071356699))

Yu, Charles. Interior Chinatown. - New York : Pantheon Books, 2020. - 270 p.; 22 cm.

ISBN (13): 9780307907196

Российская Государственная библиотека

(<https://search.rsl.ru/ru/search#q=charles%20yu%20interior%20chinatown>)

Yu, Charles. Interior Chinatown. - New York : Pantheon Books, 2020. - 270 p.; 22 cm.

ISBN (13): 9780307907196

2.2. Световни виртуални каталози

AllBookstores.com

(<https://www.allbookstores.com/Interior-Chinatown-Novel-Charles/9780307907196>)

Yu, Charles. Interior Chinatown. - New York : Pantheon Books, 2020. - 270 p.; 22 cm.

ISBN (13): 9780307907196

Amazon.com

(https://www.amazon.com/Interior-Chinatown-Novel-Vintage-Contemporaries/dp/0307948471/ref=sr_1_1?keywords=interior+chinatown+by+charles+yu&qid=1686071613&prefix=interior+chinat%2Caps%2C229&sr=8-1)

Yu, Charles. Interior Chinatown. - New York : Pantheon Books, 2020. - 270 p.; 22 cm.

ISBN (13): 9780307907196

2.3. Виртуални книготърговски материали

“Interior Chinatown” не е достъпна в български книготърговски каталози.

Изводи:

Книгата „Interior Chinatown” е отразена с метаданни в най-малко 7 чуждестранни онлайн каталога и библиотеки и в 0 виртуални български търговски каталога.

Диаграма 2. Отразяване на книгата „Interior Chinatown“ в дигитални каталози в периода 2020 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 3. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието

3.1. Анотации

Няма намерени анотации.

3.2. Резюме, реферат и съкратени версии

Не са намерени.

Изводи:

Книгата на Чарлз Ю „Interior Chinatown“ няма намерени анотации, резюмета, реферати и съкратени версии.

Фаза 4. Репродукции (деривати) на книгата

Във Фаза 4 ще бъдат търсени превод на книгата и цитирания на книгата „Interior Chinatown“ от Чарлз Ю.

4.1. Преводи

Книгата „Interior Chinatown” е преведена на френски.

Charles Yu, Aurélie Thiria-Meulemans - Chinatown, intérieur, 2020. Available from: <https://www.worldcat.org/title/1241436633> [08.06.2023]

4.2. Цитиране

Откъси от книгата „Interior Chinatown“ и цитати от нея са поместени в следните онлайн източници:

Speaking Up For Generic Asians in Charles Yu’s Interior Chinatown. In: Chapman University, Digital Commons, 2021. Available from: https://digitalcommons.chapman.edu/english_theses/50 [08.06.2023]

Charles Yu’s Interior Chinatown in Europe as an Evaluative Tool of U.S. Race Relations: “When you think American, what color do you see?”. In: SpringerLink, 07.04.2022. Available from: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-94166-6_3 [08.06.2023]

Taiwanese American discrimination in Charles Yu's novel Interior Chinatown. In eThesis In Malang, 28.03.2023. Available from: <http://etheses.uin-malang.ac.id/48628> [08.06.2023]

Изводи за Фаза 4

Книгата „Interior Chinatown“ е преведена 1 път на френски език, описани са само три цитирания на книгата, които са най подходящи, но общо е цитирана 268 (2020 г. -77; 2021 г. - 88; 2022 г. - 95; 2023 г. - 29) в онлайн източника. Резултатите от Фаза 4. Репродукция (деривация) на книгата доказват, че книгата „Interior Chinatown“ се е осъществила като медия, защото има превод на друг език.

Диаграма 3. Цитиране на “Interior Chinatown” в периода 2020 - юни 2023

Фаза 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика

5.1. Текуща (оперативна) критика

Wold. Mike. Book review: ‘Interior Chinatown’ By Charles Yu. In: Real Change, 10.03.2021. Available from: <https://www.realchangenews.org/news/2021/03/10/book-review-interior-chinatown-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

5.2. Ревюта

Lin. Ho. Interior Chinatown: A Novel. In: New York Journal of Books, 28.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.nyjournalofbooks.com/book-review/interior-chinatown-novel> [08.06.2023]

Gray. Richard. REVIEW: INTERIOR CHINATOWN BY CHARLES YU. In: The Reel Bits, 07.02.2020. Available from: <https://thereelbits.com/2020/02/07/review-interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

VanderMeer. Jeff. February’s Book Club Pick: A Devastating (and Darkly Hilarious) New Novel From the ‘Westworld’ Writer Charles Yu. In: The New York Times, 28.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/02/28/books/review/interior-chinatown-charles-yu.html> [08.06.2023]

Smith. Ken. “Interior Chinatown” by Charles Yu. In: Asian Review of Books, 08.03.2020. Available from: <https://asianreviewofbooks.com/content/interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

Fu. Jessica. WHEN BACKGROUND BECOMES FOREGROUND: CHARLES YU’S INTERIOR CHINATOWN. In: The Rumpus, 24.06.2020. Available from: <https://therumpus.net/2020/06/24/interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

Review #13: Interior Chinatown. In: charlie Reads China, 03.11.2020. Available from: <https://charliereadschina.com/2020/11/03/review-13-interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Interior Chinatown. In: Just one more pa(i)ge, 16.11.2020. Available from: <https://justonemorepaige.wordpress.com/2020/11/16/interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Shea. Roz. Interior Chinatown. In: Book Reporter, 17.11.2020. Available from: <https://www.bookreporter.com/reviews/interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Fu. Kim. Casting aspersions, Playing to type in Charles Yu's Interior Chinatown. In: TLS, 27.11.2020. Available from: <https://www.the-tls.co.uk/articles/interior-chinatown-charles-yu-review-kim-fu> [08.06.2023]

Pabilonia. Ashley. Interior Chinatown: by Charles Yu. In: Spectrum Culture, 14.12.2020. Available from: <https://spectrumculture.com/2020/12/14/interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

Interior Chinatown. In: Kirkus Reviews, 2020. Available from: <https://www.kirkusreviews.com/book-reviews/charles-yu/interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Flaxman. Jessica. Interior Chinatown By Charles Yu. In: Book Clique, 28.01.2021. Available from: <https://www.bookclique.org/2021/01/28/interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

Denslow. Josh. This gentle satire of the TV industry pokes holes in Asian-American stereotypes and tropes. In: Washington Independent Review of Books, 28.02.2021. Available from: <https://www.washingtonindependentreviewofbooks.com/index.php/bookreview/interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Hajimirsadeghi. Ashley. A review of Charles Yu’s novel Interior Chinatown. In: Ashley Hajimirsadeghi, 03.07.2021. Available from: <https://www.ashleyhajimirsadeghi.com/blog/interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

Karissa. Book Review: Interior Chinatown by Charles Yu. In: Karissa Reads Books, 23.08.2021. Available from: <https://karissareadsbooks.com/2021/08/23/book-review-interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

REVIEW - YU, “INTERIOR CHINATOWN”. In: Too Much Berard, 21.11.2021. Available from: <https://toomuchberard.com/2021/11/21/review-yu-interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Cote. Sam D. Interior Chinatown Review. In: Sam D. Cote, 20.01.2022. Available from: <https://samdcote.com/2022/01/30/interior-chinatown-review> [08.06.2023]

Book Review: Interior Chinatown by Charles Yu. In: Eustea Reads, 10.10.2022. Available from: <https://eustaciatan.com/2022/10/book-review-interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu.html> [08.06.2023]

Reading Through the Awards: Interior Chinatown, by Charles Yu. In: The Masters Review Blog, 21.01.2022. Available from: <https://mastersreview.com/reading-through-the-awards-interior-chinatown-by-charles-yu> [08.06.2023]

Interior Chinatown. In: Literary Gitane, 04.02.2022. Available from: <https://literarygitane.wordpress.com/2022/02/04/interior-chinatown> [08.06.2023]

Keaney. Quinn. Quickie Book Review: ‘Interior Chinatown’ by Charles Yu. In: What is Quinn Reading, април 2023. Available from: <https://www.whatisquinnreading.com/reviews/interior-chinatown-book-review> [08.06.2023]

5.3. Търговски и читателски класации

The 15 Best Books of 2020. In: Vanity Fair, 07.12.2020. Available from: <https://www.vanityfair.com/style/photos/2020/12/the-15-best-books-of-2020> [08.06.2023]

Temple. Emily. The Ultimate Best Books of 2020 List, 15.12.2020. Available from: <https://lithub.com/the-ultimate-best-books-of-2020-list> [08.06.2023]

The 15 Best Books of 2020. In: The Atlantic, 24.12.2020. Available from: <https://www.theatlantic.com/culture/archive/2020/12/best-books-2020/617490> [08.06.2023]

The 63 Best Books of 2020. - In: Elle, 31.12.2020. Available from: <https://www.elle.com/culture/books/g29954140/best-books-2020> [08.06.2023]

Изводи:

Книгата „Interior Chinatown” е включена в няколко класации за най-добрите книги за 2020 и има множество ревята, повечето от които позитивни. По-голямата част от ревятата са направени през годината на излизане (2020) и намаляват с времето - през 2020 има 15 ревята; през 2021 г. - 7; 2022 г. - 4; 2023 г. - 2.

Диаграма 4. Текуща (оперативна) критика в периода 2020 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 6. Експертна (научна) критика

6.1. Професионални награди

National Book Award 2020- Художествена литература

6.2. Изследвания и интерпретации

Nur. M. Taiwanese American discrimination in Charles Yu's novel Interior Chinatown.. In: Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim, 2021. Available from: <http://etheses.uin-malang.ac.id/48628> [08.06.2023]

Looney, Lori. This Week at Shain Library. In: Digital Commons, 2021. Available from:

<https://digitalcommons.conncoll.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1008&context=thhisweek> [08.06.2023]

Shilon, Orel. Speaking Up For Generic Asians in Charles Yu’s Interior Chinatown. In: Chapman University Digital Commons, 2022. Available from:

https://digitalcommons.chapman.edu/english_theses/50 [08.06.2023]

Lahiri, Madhumita. Not Going Anywhere: Local Protests as Post-global Politics. In: Duke University Press, 01.05.2022. Available from:

<https://read.dukeupress.edu/novel/article-abstract/55/1/95/313537/Not-Going-Anywhere-Local-Protests-as-Post-global> [08.06.2023]

Hassan, Asrar. Muhammad Afzal Faheem. Amina Qadeer. Metamorphoses: Tracing the Simulacra of Oriental Identity in Charles Yu’s Interior Chinatown. In: Research Gate, 2023. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Asrar-Hassan-2/publication/369235740_Metamorphoses_Tracing_the_Simulacra_of_Oriental_Identity_in_Charles_Yu's_Interior_Chinatown/links/64115a1192cfd54f84fef23c/Metamorphoses-Tracing-the-Simulacra-of-Oriental-Identity-in-Charles-Yus-Interior-Chinatown.pdf [08.06.2023]

Washington, Durthy A. Culturally Responsive Reading: Teaching Literature for Social Justice. Teachers College Press. In: Google Books, 2023. Available from:

https://www.google.bg/books/edition/Culturally_Responsive_Reading/EQmqEAAAQBAJ [08.06.2023]

Изводи:

Книгата получава само една награда през 2020 г. и е най-популярната творба на Чарлс Ю. Въпреки това има малък брой резюмета и анализи - не са открити за 2020 г., а в следващите години има по 2 анализа за всяка.

Диаграма 5. Експертна (научна) критика в периода от 2020 до 2023 г.

Фаза 7. Медиаморфози

Във Фаза 7 ще бъдат търсени медиаморфози на книгата “Interior Chinatown” на Чарлс Ю в периода 2018 - юни 2023 г.

7.1. Екранизация

През октомври 2020 г. Hulu обявява, че се разработва сериал, базиран на романа. Проектът е продуциран от самия Чарлс Ю заедно с Дан Лин, Линдзи Либераторе, Елси Чой, Миура Кайт и др. През 2022 излиза повече информация за актьорите и режисьорите. В ролите влизат Рони Чиенг, Клои Бенет и др. Режисьорите са Джафар Махмуд и Тайка Уайтити. Екранизацията още не е осъществена, но е насрочена за 2024 г.

Новини за екранизацията:

Porter. Rick. ‘Interior Chinatown’ Series a Go at Hulu, Jimmy O. Yang to Star. In: The Hollywood Reporter, 13.10.2022. Available from: <https://www.hollywoodreporter.com/tv/tv-news/hulu-interior-chinatown-series-taika-waititi-director-1235240614> [08.06.2023]

Thorne. Will. Hulu Adapting Charles Yu Novel ‘Interior Chinatown’ for Television (EXCLUSIVE). - In: Variety, 15.10.2020. Available from: <https://variety.com/2020/tv/news/hulu-charles-yus-interior-chinatown-tv-series-1234806398> [08.06.2023]

Rice. Lynette. ‘Interior Chinatown’: Diana Lin, Archie Kao & Tzi Ma Join Hulu Series. In: Deadline, 19.01.2023. Available from: <https://deadline.com/2023/01/interior-chinatown-diana-lin-archie-kao-tzi-ma-join-hulu-series-1235226844> [08.06.2023]

Interior Chinatown. - In: Premiere Date. Available from: <https://premieredate.news/tv-series/10126-interior-chinatown.html> [08.06.2023]

Interior Chinatown. - In: Internet Movie Database Inc.: IMDbPro Professional Details, 2023. Available from: <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt13354972> [08.06.2023]

Изводи:

По книгата няма направени театрална постановка, изложба или друга практика, появила се в следствие на прочита на книгата. Предвидената за 2024 г. екранизация все още не е осъществена. Въпреки това новините за нея, намерени в търсачката Google, надхвърлят милион търсения. По-голямата част от резултатите е свързана с продуцентите и актьорите, участващи в адаптацията.

Фаза 8. Историзация

Във Фаза 8 ще бъдат търсени класации, в които е включена книгата „Interior Chinatown“ на Чарлз Ю в периода 2020 -2023 г.

8.1 Класации на книгата

Книгата „Interior Chinatown“ е включена и става печеливша в „National Book Award for Fiction“ през 2020 г. в САЩ.

Charles Yu’s ‘Interior Chinatown’ wins National Book Award for Fiction. In CNN, 19.11.2020. Available from: <https://edition.cnn.com/style/article/interior-chinatown-national-book-award-intl-hnk-scli/index.html> [08.06.2023]

Изводи:

В периода 2020 - 2023 г. книгата “ Interior Chinatown” на Чарлз Ю е включена в 1 класация през 2020 г.

Диаграма 6. Класации, в които „Interior Chinatown” е включена в периода 2020 - юни 2023 г.

Изводи и обобщение

Рекапитулация на резултатите

В **Диаграма 7** може да се проследи съвкупността от всички събрани данни от информационния резонанс на книгата „Interior Chinatown” на Чарлз Ю, обособени по фази и години.

Диаграма 7. Обратна връзка с книгата “Interior Chinatown” по фази и години за периода 2020 - юни 2023 г.

За три години най-високи стойности в информационния резонанс на книгата се наблюдават във Фаза 1. Симултанни онлайн практики и пряка обратна връзка, като Фаза 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика има най-високи стойности през 2020 г.

Финален извод

Резултатите от проведеното проучване за периода 2020 - 2023 г. доказват успешното комуникиране на книгата „Interior Chinatown“ на Чарлз Ю и осъществяването ѝ като медия. Създадена е ефективна комуникация между автора и читателите.

Книгата успява да се реализира в седем от осемте фази за периода 2020 - 2023 г. Най-голям успех има във фаза 1 „Симултанни и интерактивни онлайн практики“, където общия брой на резултатите е 58. Това доказва заинтересоваността на хората и тяхната обратна връзка по отношение на книгата. Най-малък успех книгата има във фаза 3, Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието в която няма намерени резултати.

Във фаза 4, Репродукция (деривати) на книгата проведеното проучване показва, че книгата има 1 превод на френски език, и общо в търсачката на Google Scholars има 266 цитирания на книгата, като най-голяма активност има през 2022 г. Във фаза 5 „Текуща (оперативна) критика” са регистрирани общо 28 резултата. По фаза 7 и 8, книгата има 1 професионална награда и е включена в класацията за най-добри книги с жанр художествена литература, където печели и първото място. По книгата няма театрални постановки. Има предвидена екранизация през 2024 г., но все още не е осъществена.